

Spatio-Temporal Analysis of Housing Price Trajectories: The Case of Madrid (2010- 2019)

Gladys Kenyon, Dani Arribas-Bel and Caitlin Robinson

Geographic Data Science Lab
The University of Liverpool

June 2022 (Preliminary Abstract)

Summary

The first exploratory paper as part of the thesis ‘Hedonic models with machine learning’ will consider spatiotemporal variations in house prices and rents in the capital of Spain, Madrid. Ten years of property adverts in the city have been provided by online real estate company, Idealista. Divergence in house prices can provide a broader insight into geographic inequality in cities. The paper will analyse spatial house price variation over time, in order to identify clusters of high and low growth. In addition, the analysis can identify ripple effects and could be used to inform future housing policy.

KEYWORDS: House prices variation; Space- Time analysis; Neighbourhood dynamics; Madrid

1. Introduction

The residential real estate market is a key indicator of broader social processes and geographic inequality in cities. Increased migration into metropolitan areas has placed pressure on real estate markets and affordability (Van Doorn *et al.*, 2019). Creating a healthy and accessible living environment is now a key objective of local governments. Many policy initiatives, including the sustainable development goals and the 15-minute city, have focused on the impact of the housing market on quality of life. The findings of this study could inform policy initiatives at the local level of Madrid, by identifying clusters of poor-quality housing and low development. Specifically, policy relating to urban configuration and building more inclusive and liveable cities.

Historically, house prices were studied using hedonic models based on linear regression; such models have been criticized for their inability to capture housing market complexities (Selim *et al.*, 2009). Big data provides a new way to study changes in the housing market. Recent developments in real estate studies have centred around the use of ML algorithms, which are suited to large data sets and complex phenomena (Baldominos *et al.*, 2018). A machine learning approach will be used to explore convergence and ripple effects at the local level and to identify high and low growth clusters.

Madrid is the largest metropolitan areas in Spain. In 2018, Madrid had a population of 3,223,334 (INE, 2021). It has been suggested that temporal shifts in Spanish house prices have mirrored trends in Britain and Ireland, declining post-2007 and steadily rising since 2013 (The Economist, 2021). Research on the housing market in Madrid has focused on the impact of new metro lines in the city (Dorantes *et al.*,

2011).

1.3 Research Aims:

- How has the spatial pattern of housing prices and type changed over time?
- Is there evidence of spatial spillover effects between high and low growth areas?
- Can distinct 10-year trajectories in house price variation be identified?

2. Literature Review

In the last 10 years, scholars have made considerable advances in spatial data analysis in a variety of research settings. In the field of spatial econometrics, key author Anselin (1998, 2005, 2009, 2013) has emphasised the econometric issue of two kinds of spatial effects: spatial dependence and heterogeneity. Spatial dependence, or spatial autocorrelation, occurs when covariation between observations is subject to spatial ordering, the interaction is related to the spatial arrangement of observations (Anselin, 1998).

In addition, a vast amount of literature has begun to note the temporal mis-specification in spatial hedonic pricing studies, Pace *et al.* (1998) were one of the first to specify a spatiotemporal weight matrix in the HPM, they showed a houses sale price is influenced by the sales price of previously sold neighbouring properties. Gelfand *et al.* (2004) propose a hierarchical spatio-temporal HPM to capture the evolution of regional house prices.

Machine learning has also been used to investigate house price movements and forecasts in specific markets. In Australia, Milunovich (2020) employed 47 different time-series, machine learning and deep learning neural network algorithms forecast house price growth rates, noting the various performances of the models for different time horizons. ML has become a popular tool for business insights and the methods are having increasing use in the field of real estate. Specifically, predicting house prices and housing market supply and demand using ML holds many opportunities; it is useful for banks, insurances companies and governments, for example to compute real estate tax (Kontrimas and Verikas, 2011).

3. Methodology

3.1 Data

The data for the analysis is provided by Idealista, a major online real estate advertisement portal which operates across southern Europe. The data is supplemented with information taken from an official external source called Cadastre, a comprehensive register of properties created for public administrations. The dataset contains 882,732 observations over the ten-year period; each observation is a property at the individual level.

Table 1: A description of the variables in the dataset

ASSETID	Unique identifier of the advertisement	Identifier	Unique
BATHNUMBER	Number of bathrooms	Scale	0 - 99
BUITTYPEID	Dummy variable for condition	Ordinal	1 = New development 2 = Second hand to be restored 3 = Second hand in good condition
CADASTRALQUALITYID	Quality of the building	Ordinal	0 – 10 (Best - Worst)
CONSTRUCTEDAREA	Home built area in sq.m	Scale	1 - 399000
HASGARDEN	Dummy variable for garden	Nominal	0 = No garden 1 = Has garden
HASSWIMMINGPOOL	Dummy variable for swimming pool	Nominal	0 = No swimming pool 1 = Has swimming pool
HASTERRACE	Dummy variable for terrace	Nominal	0 = No terrace 1= Terrace
ISSTUDIO	Dummy variable for studio	Nominal	0 = Not studio 1 = Is studio
LATITUDE	Geographical coordinate	Scale	36.76 – 40.61
LONGITUDE	Geographical-coordinate (EPSG:4326)	Scale	-4.571 - -1.430
PERIOD	Expressed as YYYYMM, indicates the quarter when the ad was extracted. 4 quarters in total containing 3 months	Ordinal (Date)	YYYY03, YYYY06, YYYY09, YYYY12
PRICE	Asking price for the ad at Idealista expressed (€)	Scale	0 – 101,687000
ROOMNUMBER	Number of bedrooms	Scale	0 - 150
UNITPRICE	Asking price (€) per square meter (calculated using constructed area)	Scale	0 – Inf

3.2 Method

Exploratory Spatial Data Analysis (ESDA) is range of methods that can be used to identify visually and numerically variations in housing prices. The data has been aggregated into 131 areas using official administrative boundaries.

4. Results and Discussion

- Space- time statistics (morans I plot)
- Spatio- temporal visualisation of prices over time.
- Local Indicator of Spatial Autocorrelation (LISA) maps

As the analysis is yet to be completed these outputs are not included. Preliminary exploration is included below.

Figure 1: Percentage change in house price between 2011 and 2019

Figure 2: Mean house price

Figure 3: Change in average unit price 2010- 2019

References

- Anselin, L., 1988. Lagrange multiplier test diagnostics for spatial dependence and spatial heterogeneity. *Geographical analysis*, 20(1), pp.1-17.
- Anselin, L., 2005. Exploring spatial data with GeoDaTM: a workbook. *Center for spatially integrated social science*.
- Anselin, L., 2009. Spatial regression. *The SAGE handbook of spatial analysis*, 1, pp.255-276.
- Anselin, L., 2013. *Spatial econometrics: methods and models* (Vol. 4). Springer Science & Business Media.
- Baldominos, A., Blanco, I., Moreno, A.J., Iturrarte, R., Bernárdez, Ó. and Afonso, C., 2018. Identifying real estate opportunities using machine learning. *Applied sciences*, 8(11), p.2321.
- Dorantes, L.M., Paez, A. and Vassallo, J.M., 2011. Analysis of house prices to assess economic impacts of new public transport infrastructure: Madrid Metro Line 12. *Transportation research record*, 2245(1), pp.131-139.
- Gelfand, A.E., Ecker, M.D., Knight, J.R. and Sirmans, C.F., 2004. The dynamics of location in home price. *The journal of real estate finance and economics*, 29(2), pp.149-166.
- INE. 2021. *Población por capitales de provincia y sexo.(2911)*. [online] Available at: <<https://www.ine.es/jaxiT3/Datos.htm?t=2911>> [Accessed 18 August 2021].
- Kontrimas, V. and Verikas, A., 2011. The mass appraisal of the real estate by computational intelligence. *Applied Soft Computing*, 11(1), pp.443-448
- Pace, R.K., Barry, R., Clapp, J.M. and Rodriguez, M., 1998. Spatiotemporal autoregressive models of neighborhood effects. *The Journal of Real Estate Finance and Economics*, 17(1), pp.15-33.
- The Economist, 2021. *Global house prices*. [online] The Economist. Available at: <<https://www.economist.com/graphic-detail/global-house-prices>> [Accessed 18 August 2021].
- Van Doorn, L., Arnold, A. and Rapoport, E., 2019. In the age of cities: The impact of urbanisation on house prices and affordability. In *Hot Property* (pp. 3-13). Springer, Cham.

Biographies

I am currently a second-year student on the CDT Data Analytics and Society, integrated MSc and PhD. I have a first-class BA in Geography.